

Against the mummification: a perspective in preservation and conservation of cultural heritage in digital archives.

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ABSTRACT

From the perspective of the Visual and Cultural Studies, it will be addressed the problems arising from the preservation and conservation of cultural objects contained in electronic devices with reduced half-life. The present text takes as a starting point the philosophical postulates of Jean Baudrillard and Michell Foucault, to release a deliberation on the challenges faced by the areas of conservation, preservation, curatorship and exhibition of artistic pieces, in the face of the digital storage devices' technical deficit and organized fragility. It will be focussed as studies' cases: Cinema's Lost Films, and the phenomena surrounding the preservation and conservation of video games.

Key words: Cultural heritage, Art preservation, Visual Studies, Cinema, Video games.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is convenient to start delimiting the terminologies: conservation and preservation: Rodolfo Peláez points out that at the moment of studying artistic and cultural objects, it is preponderant to establish the distinction between *conservation* and *preservation*. Although *conservation* starts from the idea of obtaining and storing the original artistic pieces, aspiring to avoid or diminish its degradation, one of its major implications, is what Baudrillard warns us as *death by museomummification*, that is, the cryogenization of culture (Baudrillard, 1983). While the *preservation* implies the classification and proper maintenance of the original pieces so that the public has access to them, denoting that if there is no access to said pieces it is not being preserved. The core point of preservation is the perspective of the use, and the construction of new discourses based on the artistic pieces (Peláez, 2004).

A starting point: Avoiding common scenarios product of assuming human evolution as a linear path rather than a rhizome, we could start from the optimistic outlook that the art world is shaped by how society produces and acquires images, and that was irreversibly impacted with the arrival of reproduction technologies: initially with presses, serial printing techniques, the development of photography, cinematography, devices for production, storage and reproduction of audio and video, storage devices digital, and even telephony.

All those artifacts of image reproduction allowed the massification of art, and an apparent democratization of it. Since the unprecedented printing systems, the literature and the plastic arts, they were already reproducible and mass distributed, making these

productions considerably more accessible. In a very short period of time - historically speaking - the social classes that were previously excluded from artistic circuits, thanks to the technology of production and reproduction of the image, could now access books, paintings, and eventually, the music, photography, cinematography and other forms of art that were previously constrained to certain moments, spaces or social circuits. The reproduction of the image, and the mass accessibility of it to the large social groups, eroded the mystical aura of art (Berger, 1990), the art that was only accessible to the economic and social elites or to certain spatial, temporal and rituals; now it was potentially art for the masses, since it was mass distributed. Eventually any individual could voluntarily or accidentally access to the artistic, religious, political and commercial images.

Setting in motion the perfect *emulation* described by Michael Foucault: a similarity without contact, in which things can be imitated from one end of the universe to the other, without chaining or proximity; *Emulation* is the mirror-like twinness of things (Foucault, 2002). A *gemelity* that erases the idea of original and replica, ideas addressed by Baudrillard's philosophy (Baudrillard, 1983), and Phillip K. Dirk's literature (2007), reasoning that it is impossible to discern the original and the replica, since all we see are *replicants, emulations*.

John Berger points out that the apparatuses of the art market were quivering in the face of the death of the mystical aura due to exclusivity, and being aware of what Baudrillard exposes as a dissolution between original versus copy (Baudrillard, 1983), a primeval

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piece against replicant. The art market sought to generate new mystical figures, now concentrated around authenticity (Berger, 1990), with which they sought to establish that the value of art revolved around the superior value of a primeval piece -original-, in front of the replicants pieces -copies. In an attempt to preserve the elitist status of art, comparable to the status prior to the mass production and reproduction of the image.

This prosthetic memory: (Gibson, 2012) which we call technology, since the end of the 19th century it has facilitated the construction of a legacy and cultural testimony that allows us to preserve *the voices of the dead*. These *voices of the dead* that are not only preserved individually in the memory of the living, or that are constructed from the mental exercise of the imagination. Prosthetic memory, in its various manifestations, such as film tapes, magnetic tapes, vinyl, acetates, transistors, punched cards, data storage disks, etc. allows the living to literally see and hear to Julio Cortazar of 1977 explaining his creative attempt to discourse in innovative ways the relationship between the reader and the text (Cortazár, 1977). We are surrounded by millions of voices of the dead, stored in music, films, video games, and other expressions of art.

Such prosthetic memory, as a technological, cultural, material and artistic product, has an inescapable relationship with objects, and objects are finite in nature. Within the field of art, objects are not exempt from death, and within the changes of paradigms proposed by modern and contemporary art is the production of pieces destined for gradual or sudden disappearance. Whether it was part of a proposal against evanescence or because they were made with materials with little experimentation that were very fragile or unstable. Consequently, the activities related to Culture and Art seems to be closely related to the preservation of objects. Therefore, added to the already known challenges of preservation of objectual art, on how to face the progressive degradation of materials, such as pigments, emulsions, supports, etc., now diverse artistic proposals face the organized fragility of digital electronic devices: the fragility of prosthetic memory.

Cinematography since its detonation as an audiovisual narrative art has been appreciated and embraced by popular culture, art and academia alike. But despite such influence and appreciation, it has not been immune to the death of the object. Such mortality of the object is expressed specifically with the so-called **Lost Films:**

which are feature films or short films, and that is speculated, do not exist in any file or collection. In its edition of June 14, 1998, the Argentine Newspaper La Nación (1998), presented a series of statements by researcher Larry Karr, in which he explains that 48 percent of the 21,000 American films produced before 1950 have been lost definitively and of the 846 titles produced in the United States by 1918, only 29 are preserved intact in the American public archives, and another 27 are in European collections. The reason for such an exponential disappearance is due to the fact that such films, when produced in nitrate-based tapes, that are particularly unstable, flammable and, due to the emission of the gases inherent in the materials used to manufacture them, the emulsion is gradually destroyed. Damaging and even destroying the content of the film. Intriguing to the global figure in which it is calculated that 50 percent of the films before 1950 and 80 percent of the films produced during the silent film period have been lost forever.

Mexico's film heritage has been one of the victims of the flammable nature of tapes. On March 24, 1982 at the Cineteca Nacional in Mexico City the flames consumed the film collection that was housed there. It is speculated that 6 thousand films were totally destroyed and it has been impossible to determine with precision how many films were unique pieces (Ventura, 2012). A similar case occurred in 1937, when the warehouse of the Twentieth Century Fox in Little Ferry, New Jersey, caught fire, destroying all the original negatives of that producer and other smaller studios, prior to 1935 (1937).

To the flammable nature of the nitrate-based films as accelerators of the destruction of the cinematographic story, we can also add the technical, legal, political and economic factors that obstruct or hinder the preservation of those pieces (García, 1998). Moving films in nitrate-based tape to more stable materials such polyester tapes or transferring them to digital media, means to be able to pay the high costs of translation and digitization, and few of these films have its copy rights released of commercial use, being the cause why, from a strict legal perspective, to carry out the translation, reproduction, total or partial distribution of those materials is considered illegal, reason why in many cases the only versions to which it has access the general public are those that have been called bootleg, pirates or contraband (Stoklasa and Bauman, 2013).

If cinematography with all its cultural dominance could not prevent the death of its objects, the prospects of

survival for other artistic media and prosthetic memory are far from optimistic. Especially those that make use of electronic and digital storage devices. The information contained in digital and electronic devices is at risk of disappearing, due to its fallible nature (Lowood et al., 2009), what does the above mean?. Digital data storage devices, for example: discs hard drives, cd-roms, servers, etc., have turned out to be extremely fragile, they are technological devices with a considerably reduced useful life (Vries & Harrington, 2016). That is, digital data storage devices are easily damaged by external factors, such as humidity, heat, careless use, etc. In addition, that the technological iteration, transforms most of these artifacts into archaisms in a very short time. This process can also be found in the software, in which in a very short time it is incompatible or inoperative. All of the above, responding to the cultural phenomenon that Baudrillard called how: technical deficit or organized fragility, that is, the objects are not expected to last, in order that a new generation of objects occupy their place. Therefore, objects cannot escape death (Baudrillard, 2007).

Before it falls into oblivion: Continuing with the premise that all the pieces of art contained in digital and electronic devices are at risk of disappearing, due to its fallible nature, and that each year that passes the risk increases. Thousands of pieces are closer to its disappearance; it is important that we generate reflections away from prejudice. Such reflections must come from scholars, restaurateurs, curators, enthusiasts, collectors, artists and producers. Since in the absence of a synergy between the various fronts interested in the appreciation, enjoyment, restoration, healing, study and production of artistic and cultural products, any approach, opinion, or resolution runs the risk of being sterile, ill-informed, prejudiced or even harmful. And every moment that these reflections are postponed, it is a moment in which more and more pieces are in danger of disappearing.

Considering that videogames are designed with the intention that they are pieces in which they can be transgressed, not only to contemplate, they can pose paradoxes at the moment of being preserved, since when using storage to avoid their degradation, the main intention for it was created is cancelled. The concealment cancels the role of receiver and reader accomplice (Cortazar, 1977). The piece, when is tried to be saved, has been materially mummified, experiencing what Baudrillard calls: *death by museomification* (Baudrillard, 1983). A video game that cannot be transgressed, loses its value and function

as a piece of art. Therefore, the efforts of preservation, conservation and restoration should focus their exertions on allowing future generations of readers to go through and transgress these types of pieces. A non-operative videogame, which cannot be accessed, transgressed, travelled and played, becomes an inoperative archaism, a vestige of a cryogenic culture (Baudrillard, 1983).

Within the efforts in the field of the restoration and preservation of videogames as operative objects, one of the main actors, active in the year 2017, is Artemio Urbina, Mexican, who has sought to document the hardware and software of various videogame platforms, pretending to register the available information in the subjects of collecting, maintenance and repair of videogame devices. It has been interested in generating networks among participants, in order to exchange information, technical support and documentation of processes. Artemio Urbina maintains an openly critical stance against the market models that surround videogames, from the field of price speculation that involves the sale of pieces between enthusiasts and collectors, to the legal implications of the commercial industry of the digital sale of videogames, which seem to be one of the factors that impose the greater resistance to the preservation of video games. Urbina maintains an open skepticism about emulation as an art preservation tactic, since it argues that it is only a temporary solution, that it would even generate another series of challenges, starting from the premise that emulators, being pieces of software, follow the technological iteration and will eventually become obsolete and inoperative, so in the future not only would the preservation of the art pieces per se, it will be required, that the interested parties would be forced to look for alternatives to keep the emulators operational. He advocates to continue exploring and developing exact replicas of hardware that allow the execution of the art pieces as they were executed in their native systems (Urbina and Zuratzi, 2017). The main advantage of such a position is that no modifications are made to the pieces of software, keeping the prosthetic memory intact.

Although it is an inevitable fact that objects die, and, that the prosthetic memory is transmuted into an inoperative archaism, buried between the sands of the deserts of the mind. Just as there are artists who intentionally advocate the ruin of their work, there are artists whose work is prematurely degraded due to ignorance of the materials used. What position should the culture take in front of such objects? What position

should artists take? Facing the premature ruin of their work? Hundreds of cultural objects, are produced within the industrial, commercial and artistic circuit. Are their producers aware of the premature death of their pieces? Is the ruin of these objects part of their artistic intention?

Baudrillard argues that our culture and its linear vision of its existence runs the risk of collapsing if we do not put at face value to the *acquis* that we have produced. For the simple accumulation means, and means from the sense that it nourishes nostalgia, and, nostalgia is the parodic ghost of the restoration of the lost referent. Hiltrud Schinzer (Morera, 2016) reflected on the position of Cesaré Brandi, and suggested that the restoration profession is an utopian activity faced with the impossibility of recovering an earlier state. Such is the confrontation between the thought of the utopian intention to keep pieces stored but intact, stored, killed by museumification. Inactive artifacts in a desert of old signs and things. What was the jungle of signs and things (Ranciere, 2008) that provides the way to the great desert of the mind, is it really possible to make them bloom again?

John Berger argues that fear of the present leads to the mystification of the past, and directly to the mystification of art, which is manipulated to preserve ideas of social construction, aristocratic and plutocratic ideas about the consumption of the image (Berger, 1990). Although, seeking to maintain a critical vision, and being aware that the history of art makes an abuse of the concept of art, appropriating objects and calling them as art (Rabadán, 2017), either to respond to the dynamics of the art market, political or social, and often legitimizes objects or phenomena that allow to perpetuate those mentioned. We should not divert our gaze from a large number of artistic productions that we do not take responsibility for, we cannot forget that the artistic phenomenon is allowed, and allows us to return to the fundamental questions, and, in such a function, we can find the value artistic.

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